

Oracle Based Approach of Proof for Complexity Classes

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ABSTRACT

Here we are to give the full incompleteness of oracle-based proofs of inequivalence of complexity classes.

Keywords: P versus NP, oracle, proof, complexity classes.

INTRODUCTION

The statement of theorem has a long-standing history [1]. We are considering the latest research using oracle-approach of proof [2], as well as our result on the “as is” incompatibility of complexity classes [3].

The oracle and Turing automata have a review in [4, 5].

DISCUSSION

Since oracle is posed as a separate element of the proof, however, as we know the separation leads to a ‘greedy’ and unknown strategy ignoring the certificate relation ‘as is’.

As we know, if there is the set of certificate relations then we can inverse and build the set of alphabetical trees of the accepted words in Turing automata [6] which is polynomial in time, space and, thus, complexity.

CONCLUSION

We have shown that oracle-based proofs of $P \leftrightarrow NP$ lead to the same fact of the certificate and relation set which is polynomial and, thus, leads to another argument towards the incompleteness of this fact in the full proof.

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